

The Flexos Shoulder Exoskeleton for Weight Lifting Assistance

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Abstract—In this paper we present Flexos, a fully portable shoulder exoskeleton developed for logistic and industrial tasks. The device presents a simplified design with only a single, series elastic actuated joint employing an active torque control that assists the user in performing weight-lifting tasks. The device is lightweight and can be easily worn as a backpack. The exoskeleton has a hyper-redundant kinematic chain connecting the backpack to the main SEA, which exerts torque on the upper arm. We performed preliminary experiments on seven healthy subjects: the exoskeleton allowed covering almost all the shoulder range of motion and the assistance it provided resulted in an average reduction of muscular effort.

I. INTRODUCTION

Despite advancements in the robotics sector and the growing number of applications deployed in industrial scenarios, there are still tasks requiring the flexibility of human operators. Unfortunately some of these tasks, such as repeatedly lifting and moving objects in unstructured environments, can have a bad impact on workers leading to medical conditions known as work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs). WMSDs accounts for 15% of total healthcare costs in the EU-28, affecting three out of five workers [1].

While robots still cannot replace humans in these tasks, portable wearable robots can be a valuable tool for the prevention of WMSDs, as also suggested by the increasing demand of portable upper limb exoskeletons to be deployed in industrial and logistic workplaces [2]. Soft exoskeleton, with respect to the mostly common rigid ones, are extremely light and they fully prevent the discomfort caused by the joint misalignment issue, typical in rigid devices and especially relevant for the shoulder complex. However, soft exoskeletons usually provides only a limited amount of torque, due to the structural performance of the soft garments used [3].

The nature of the actuation system represents a fundamental feature, since the most used solutions until now are passive, i.e. they are based on passive energy storage systems such as springs. Despite being extremely light and simple, the torque provided to the user cannot be set in real-time. Series Elastic Actuators (SEAs) make a great design candidate for an exoskeleton with an active actuation system. SEAs estimate the interaction torque by measuring the angular displacement of the elastic joint, providing feedback torque data for enabling real-time closed-loop torque control, which

Fig. 1. The proposed exoskeleton for the shoulder.

ensures safe physical Human Robot Interaction (pHRI) [4]. However, these systems are usually bulkier and heavier than their passive counterparts and exoskeletons employing many actively actuated joints may present excessive weight, thus compromising portability and ergonomics.

To make the most of active exoskeletons' benefits while having a lightweight solution, we designed a portable, active and under-actuated shoulder exoskeleton weighing 3.8 Kg excluding the battery. The device is equipped with a SEA and it is meant to assist the worker in repeated weight lifting and moving objects tasks.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

Flexos is designed to be wearable as a backpack thanks to a primary back interface made of a soft brace sewn together with a 3D printed and ergonomic-shaped back skeleton. Starting from the backpack, a kinematic chain - the flexible link adapted from our previous work [5] - acts in parallel to the human arm, allowing the user to move the arm around the internal/external rotation axis and to move the shoulder center of rotation around the acromioclavicular joint. The flexible link ends in the SEA, whose torque is transferred through a secondary 3d printed arm interface to the human arm. The SEA has been characterized in our previous work [6] and its measurements mapped to the correspondent joint torque value, which is used to implement a precise closed-loop torque controller - Fig. 2 - whose main goal is to partially compensate gravity torque due to the arm weight - and eventually a lifted object weight - during elevation motion. Flexos is fully portable; the battery - 1 Kg -, the control unit,

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Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the implemented torque controller.

and the wireless communication system are all embedded in the exoskeleton backpack. The system can be continuously operated, without need for recharging the battery, for at least 6 hours.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

A pilot study was conducted on seven healthy subjects to assess the efficacy of the exoskeleton in assisting the user during tasks involving upper limb elevation; for this reason, the experimental protocol tasks have been designed to assess both the upper limb Range Of Motion (ROM) when wearing the exoskeleton and the reduction of the muscular effort required to perform the tasks. ROM evaluation is achieved thanks to the exoskeleton IMU located on the arm interface. The muscular effort, instead, is tested by measuring the electromyography activity (EMG) of five targeted muscles - biceps brachii (IBIC), anterior deltoid (aDEL), medial deltoid (mDEL), pectoralis major (mPEC) and upper trapezius (uTRA) - during static and dynamic weight-lifting tasks. The tasks involving EMG measurements are repeated in two different conditions, with (w. Exo) and without (w.o. Exo) the exoskeleton. Results shows how the device allows covering almost all the shoulder ROM - 89.2% flexion/extension and 88.4% internal/external rotation, Tab. I -. Moreover, the exoskeleton provided assistance resulted in an average (-31.6% static - Fig. 3 -, -24.6% dynamic - Fig. 4 -) reduction of muscular effort. We believe our concept is promising and that could pave the way to a workplace scenario where robots do not replace humans but provide them a valuable asset for preventing the insurgence of WMSDs.

TABLE I

MEAN \pm STD OF SHOULDER ROM. DATA FOR HEALTHY SUBJECTS FROM [7], COMPARED TO THE ROM COVERED WITH OUR EXOSKELETON.

	w.o. Exo [7]	w. Exo
Flexion	166.7° \pm 4.7°	149.2° \pm 9.24°
Extension	62.3° \pm 9.5°	55.1° \pm 9.0°
Internal Rot.	68.8° \pm 4.6°	66.7° \pm 4.9°
External Rot.	103.7° \pm 8.5°	85.7° \pm 3.4°

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Fig. 3. Static task. The reduction was significant for the medial deltoid and pectoralis major. Error bars show the standard error.

Fig. 4. Dynamic task. (a) Mean (solid) and standard deviation (shaded) of the pattern of activation of the muscles, averaged over repetitions, for one representative subject, both w. Exo (red) and w.o. Exo (gray). (b) Average and standard error of the averaged value over repetitions and subjects. The reduction was significant for mDEL and mPEC.

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